

HAEMATOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE FRESH WATER FISH, *CYPRINUS CARPIO* EXPOSED TO SUB-LETHAL CONCENTRATION OF PISCICIDAL COMPOUNDS FROM *CESTRUM SPECIES* (FAM : SOLANACEAE)

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ABSTRACT : The sub-lethal concentration of the active principal of two piscicidal plants viz. *Cestrum nocturnum* (2.8 mg⁻¹) and *Cestrum diurnum* (3.2 mg⁻¹) induced the haematological changes in a freshwater fish *Cyprinus carpio*. Behavioural activities such as erratic swimming, loss of reflex, hyperventilation increased surfacing and jerk movements were observed. The total number of erythrocytes, leukocytes, and haemoglobin concentration and packed cell volume declined while erythrocytes sedimentation rate and related parameters like MCH, MCHC, MCV altered with exposure. Since the plant toxins influence cell integrity and hemopoiesis, the oxygen carrying capacity of blood was decreased, consequently thermodynamic and metabolic activity in fish was disturbed, therefore *Cestrum* species seems to be Karyocytophilic and Cytokaryophilic toxins to the fish.

Key words : *Cestrum nocturnum*, *Cestrum diurnum*, *Cyprinus carpio*, Piscicidal plants.

INTRODUCTION

The applications of haematological studies to the investigation of animal and human disease progress is well accepted and considered to be routine procedure in diagnostic methods. There have been attempts to apply haematological parameter to the study of abnormal physiological processes in fish (Celik, 2004 and Gabriel *et al.*, 2009); However the haematological parameters in relation with toxicant stress to Indian fishes were studied in recent past by various ichthyologists (Ghazaly, 1991 and Raizada & Singh, 1980), while the studies on the effect of piscicidal compounds of plants on fish are scanty (Bhatt & Singh, 1985; Bhatt *et al.*, 1987; Bhatt & Farswan, 1992; Olufayo, 2009 and Gabriel *et al.*, 2009). Piscicidal (Fish poison) compounds of plant origin were studied by various workers for their use in aquaculture to remove predatory and weed fishes (Konar, 1973; Chowdhary, 1968 and Singh *et al.*, 1996). But very less efforts have been made to evaluate the mechanism of poisoning in fish through plant piscicides. *Cestrum* species are recently reported to be a bio-cidal plant (Patil and Jawale, 2002). Despite its poisonous nature, it also showed remarkable pharmacological activities (Roy & Chatterjee, 1962 and Chatterjee & Ray, 1964). *Cestrum* species are well evaluated for its phytochemicals like saponins, alkaloid, hydrocarbons, tannins, sterols, fatty acids and essential oil by various workers (Riaz & Chaudhari, 1993; Haraguchi *et al.*, 1999 and Ahmad *et al.*, 1993). Therefore to evaluate the mechanism of poisoning, the present study was carried out on haematological changes in *Cyprinus carpio* induced by plant piscicides of *Cestrum nocturnum* and *Cestrum diurnum* (Family : Solanaceae) at different sub-lethal doses which are useful in detection and diagnosis of fish death.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Piscicidal plant *Cestrum nocturnum* and *Cestrum diurnum* were cultivated in garden, their essences were collected, shed dried, and powdered mechanically. The saponins of *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum* were isolated by the method of Chakravarti *et al.* (1963, 1962). The leaves were extracted with ethanol. The extract were hydrolysed with NaCl and HCl mixed with aqueous butanol and repeatedly crystallised with aqueous alcohol. The concentrated residue was evaporated to dryness to yield crystalline saponins of m.p. 242°C and 269°C from *C. diurnum* and *C. nocturnum* respectively. The isolated compounds were dried and 1% aqueous solution of each compound was prepared to be use. The healthy freshwater fish *C. carpio* were collected from the nearby rearing ponds and kept in tank having a continues supply of dechlorinated water and standard food. Water temperature was maintained at 20±3°C. Fish mortality rate was less than 1% and fish were maintained in the tank for the period of upto six weeks. Ten fishes were exposed to the pre-determined sub-lethal concentration of each toxicant such as 2.8 mg⁻¹ (*C. nocturnum*), 3.2 mg⁻¹ (*C. diurnum*) for 48 hrs (Jawale, 2002). A control set was also maintained. After 48 hrs alive fishes from each set were bleed by cardiac puncture. Bleeding was accomplished in less than one minute after each fish was removed from the holding tank. Blood was collected in heparinized syringe, using a 27 gauge hypodermic needle. Physical resistant without anesthetic was used in blood collection. Various haematological parameters such as haemoglobin content (Hb), total erythrocyte count (TEC), packed cell volume (PCV), total leukocyte count (TLC) were estimated using methods described by Dacie and Lewis (1963). Absolute value were determined using the formulae

as, mean cell haemoglobin concentration (MCHC) was calculated by dividing the haemoglobin content in gm/1000 ml by the PCV/1000 ml of blood. (MCH) was determined from the haemoglobin value (Hb) and from the erythrocyte count. Results were express as mean \pm standard error of mean (SEM) and differences between means were considered to be significant when $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fish shows remarkable alteration in the behaviours on exposure to toxicant such as, erratic swimming movements,

jerk, escaping the toxicant, uncontrolled, imbalanced swimming, convulsion, surfacing, engulf of air and suffocation behaviour. The mean values for the haematological parameters of *C. carpio* studied are shown in Table.1. There was significant alteration in the haematological values after 48 h. expose to plant toxicant. The result indicates that the haemoglobin percentage, packed cell volume, total number of erythrocytes and leukocytes were decline, while erythrocytes sedimentation rate increased with *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum* as compared to control fish. Other absolute values (MCV, MCHC and MCH) also altered in response to the changes in above parameters.

Table 1 : Mean values of body length, body weight and various haematological parameters of control and treated individuals of *Cyprinus carpio* exposed to sublethal concentration of *C. nocturnum* (2.8 mg⁻¹) and *C. diurnum* (3.2 mg⁻¹) for 48 hours.

Parameter	Control	Fish treated with	
		<i>C. nocturnum</i>	<i>C. diurnum</i>
Body length (cm)	13.23 \pm 0.20	13.40 \pm 0.42	12.14 \pm 0.01
Body wt. (gm)	26.39 \pm 0.00	28.61 \pm 0.00	24.40 \pm 0.07
Hb (gm/100 ml)	12.8 \pm 0.02	4.40 \pm 0.04	6.20 \pm 0.02
PCV (%)	36.07 \pm 0.03	18.02 \pm 0.05	22.58 \pm 0.12
MCH (pg)	45.28 \pm 0.76	119.69 \pm 0.34	102.39 \pm 0.02
MCHC (gm/lit)	33.28 \pm 0.12	26.28 \pm 0.09	23.28 \pm 0.02
MCV (μm^3)	132.27 \pm 0.54	412.40 \pm 0.59	422.10 \pm 0.72
Total no. of RBC (1000/mm ³)	4.72 \pm 0.36	2.32 \pm 0.27	3.03 \pm 0.18
Total no. of WBC (1000/mm ³)	4.30 \pm 0.02	2.89 \pm 0.28	3.32 \pm 0.42
ESR (mm/h)	1.8962 \pm 0.063	3.79 \pm 0.072	3.01 \pm 0.081

*Mean values with standard deviation (+SD).

Legend : PCV - Packed cell volume, Hb - Haemoglobin, MCHC - Mean corpuscular haemoglobin concretion
ESR - Erythrocyte sedimentation rate.

Fish being a very successful group of vertebrate, has adapted a wide range of environmental conditions, however at the same time, they are highly sensitive to the environmental stress. The results of present study indicated that the entry of plant compounds into the blood stream of fish, promotes their ill effects on various blood parameters. The reduction in red cell count and haemoglobin percentage indicates the occurrence of acute anaemia. Such anaemia in fishes is known to induce by various toxicants (Agrawal *et al.*, 1982, 1983). The anaemia might be due to deficiency of iron, leading to decrease in haemoglobin synthesis (Sharma & Gupta, 1982; Olufayo, 2009 and Nanda & Behera, 1996). It can also be inferred that erythropenia might be due to the disturbance in metabolism of the haemopoietic organs (Shammi and Quayyum, 1982) or due to increased in the rate of erythrocytes destruction (Agrawal and Srivastava, 1980).

Plant toxicants of saponin group are reported to be haemolytic in nature (George *et al.*, 2002). Bhatt and Faraswan (1992) had observed the ruptured cell membrane, nuclear membrane, reduction in size of nuclei and vacuolated cytoplasm in the RBCs of fish exposed to *Aesculus indica* (Colebr), *Engelhardtia colebrookiana* (Linn), *Lyonia ovalifolia* (Wall) and *Zanthoxylum alatum* (Roxb) containing plant chemicals.

Olufayo (2009), elucidate that haemolysis and injury in the blood cell made the fish inefficient to take up the oxygen required for its survival. As red cell number and haemoglobin concentration reflects the oxygen carrying efficiency of the blood and need of oxygen, in carrying out normal behaviours of the fish. Agrawal *et al.* (1982), described lymphocytopenia, haemorrhages and oedema, decreases the total number of erythrocytes, leukocytes and haemoglobin percentage in intoxicated fishes.

The change in MCV, MCHC and MCH in plant toxicant treated fishes suggested the destruction of RBCs, which result in reduced oxygen carrying capacity and ultimately death of fish. The reduced WBCs and RBCs concentration reflect the plant toxicant induced cell lysis. It was apparent at this level, the gills and body of the toxicated fish become pale whitish or colour less in contrast to the normal individuals in which the gills were dark reddish. Thus saponins of *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum* could be considered as Karyocytophilic and Cytokaryophilic toxins to the fish. The increased erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and decreased packed cell volume (PCV) accounted for the degradation of blood proteins in the fish as observed by Bhatt (1985) on injecting certain plant alkaloid and tannins.

Thus the active ingredient of both piscicidal plants definitely influenced the dynamicity of haemopoiesis in fish, and therefore the oxygen carrying capacity of the blood was gradually decreases. At this level because of high CO₂ and low O₂ tension, blood was quit unable to compensate the deficit oxygen budget of the cell and organs of fish; which intern affected the thermodynamics and metabolic activities of the fish (Faraswan, 1989). Consequently such condition might have proved a contributory factor to anaemia and ultimately death in the fishes toxified with *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum*.

Further work is in progress to evaluate *C. nocturnum* as fish toxicant to be used in aquaculture to remove predatory and weed fishes during pond reclamation.

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